

An Exploratory Analysis of the Programmes and Strategies for Poverty Alleviation in Rural India

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Abstract

Poverty and unemployment have been the bane of India since long. Their reduction has been one of the major goals of India's development planning since the beginning of the planning era in 1951-52 and the planning process has been sensitive to the needs of the poor. Accordingly, the Government of India has launched various programmes from time to time with an aim to alleviate poverty and unemployment, and to create adequate livelihood opportunities for the poor through provision of employment and public services. Poverty alleviation schemes and programmes have been in pace for a long time now. The programmes and schemes have been modified, consolidated, expanded and improved over time. The targeted programmes fall into four broad categories, (a) self-employment programmes (b) wage-employment programmes (c) public distribution system (PDS) and (d) other social welfare-oriented programmes (SWOP), such as National Social Assistance programme (NSAP), the Aam Admi Bima Yojana (AABY) and the Rashtriya Swasthya Bima Yojana (RSBY).

Poverty can effectively be eradicated only when the poor start contributing to the growth by their active involvement in the growth process. Implementation of the programmes should be increasingly based on approaches and methods which involve the poor themselves in the process of poverty eradication and economic growth. This is possible through a process of social mobilisation, encouraging participatory approaches and institutions and empowerment of the poor. In this the PRIs, the voluntary organisations and community-based Self-Help Groups will be more closely involved.

In 1951, 47 percent of India's rural population was below the poverty line. The proportion went up to 64 percent in 1954-55 and it came down to 45 percent in 1960- 61 but in 1977-78, it went up again to 51 percent. Poverty declined significantly between the mid-1970s and the end of the 1980s. The decline was more pronounced between 1977-78 and 1986-87, with rural poverty declining from 51 percent to 39 percent. It went down further to 34 percent by 1989-90. Urban poverty went down from 41 percent in 1971-78 to 34 percent in 1986-87 and further to 33 percent in 1989-90. The post-economic reform period evidenced both progress and setbacks. Rural poverty increased from 34 percent in 1989-90 to 43 percent in 1992, and then fell to 37 percent in 1993-94. Undoubtedly, India has made some progress in the reduction of poverty. Yet, in 2004-05, as many as 302 million persons (27.5 percent) were living below the poverty line in India. A large number of the hardcore poor are located in remote and inaccessible areas. There were many major poverty alleviation programmes introduced during 1950-1990.

This paper will provide an overview of different programmes, policies and strategies for eliminating poverty and unemployment in rural areas.

Keywords: poverty, unemployment, programmes, policies, strategies, rural etc.

Introduction

Poverty and unemployment have been the bane of India since long. Their reduction has been one of the major goals of India's development planning since the beginning of the planning era in 1951-52 and the planning process has been sensitive to the needs of the poor. Accordingly, the Government of India has launched various programmes from time to time with an aim to alleviate poverty and unemployment, and to create adequate livelihood opportunities for the poor through provision of employment and public services. The programmes and schemes have been modified, consolidated, expanded and improved over time. The targeted programmes fall into four broad categories, (a) self-employment programmes (b) wage-employment programmes (c) public distribution system (PDS) and (d) other social welfare-oriented programmes (SWOP), such as National Social Assistance programme (NSAP), the Aam Admi Bima Yojana (AABY) and the Rashtriya Swasthya Bima Yojana (RSBY). There are numerous centrally sponsored schemes (CSS) belonging to all the four categories. The CSS are designed by the Centre, administered by the Ministry of Rural Development, but implemented by the state governments, which generally contributes 25 percent of their cost. In addition, some state governments have their own schemes.

Poverty eradication is one of the major objectives of planned development. The magnitude of the problem is still quite staggering. Thirty-six per cent of the Indian population was below poverty line (BPL) in 1993-94, the latest year for which the data are available and the absolute number of poor was 320 million, out of which 244 million (37 per cent of the rural population) lived in rural areas. The incidence of poverty declined from 54.9 per cent in 1973-74 to 36 per cent in 1993-94. But the absolute number of poor did not decline much over this period of 20 years. There were 321 million poor in 1973-74 and 320 million in 1993-94; in the rural areas the corresponding numbers were 261 million and 244 million.

The main determinants of poverty are (i) lack of income and purchasing power attributable to lack of productive employment and considerable underemployment and not to lack of employment per se; (ii) a continuous increase in the price of food, especially foodgrains which account for 70-80 per cent of the consumption basket; and (iii) inadequacy of social infrastructure, affecting the quality of life of the people and their employability.

The Government recognizes that high growth of incomes is by itself not enough to improve the quality of life of the poor. Unless all the citizens of the country, and most particularly the poor, have certain basic minimum services, their living conditions cannot improve. These minimum services include among other things literacy education, primary health care, safe drinking water and nutritional security. The Government had convened a meeting of Chief Ministers to identify such basic minimum services and a list of seven services had unanimously been agreed upon. These seven services are safe drinking water, primary health facilities, universal primary education, nutrition to school and pre-school children, shelter for the poor, road connectivity for all villages and habitations, and the Public Distribution System (PDS) with a focus on the poor.

Poverty can effectively be eradicated only when the poor start contributing to the growth by their active involvement in the growth process. Implementation of the programmes should be increasingly based on approaches and methods which involve the poor themselves in the process of poverty eradication and economic growth. This is possible through a process of social mobilisation, encouraging participatory approaches and institutions and empowerment

of the poor. In this the PRIs, the voluntary organisations and community-based Self-Help Groups will be more closely involved.

Programmes and Strategies for Poverty Alleviation in Rural Areas

- **Integrated Rural Development Programme (IRDP)**

IRDP in India is among the world's most ambitious programs to alleviate rural poverty by providing income-generated assets to the poorest of the poor. This program was first introduced in 1978-79 in some selected areas, but covered all the areas by November 1980. Integrated Rural Development Programme was initiated on October 2, 1980. The main objective of IRDP is to raise families of identified target group below poverty line by creation of sustainable opportunities for self-employment in the rural sector. Assistance is given in the form of subsidy by the government and term credit advanced by financial institutions (commercial banks, cooperatives and regional rural banks.) The program is implemented in all blocks of the country as centrally sponsored scheme funded on 50:50 basis by the center and the states. The target group under IRDP consists of small and marginal farmers, agricultural laborers and rural artisans having annual income below Rs. 11,000 defined as poverty line in the Eighth Plan. Furthermore, 40 per cent of the coverage should be of women beneficiaries and 3 per cent of physically challenged persons. At the grassroots level, the block staff is responsible for implementation of the program. The State Level Coordination Committee (SLCC) monitors the program at state level whereas the Ministry of Rural Areas and Employment is responsible for the release of central share of funds, policy formation, overall guidance, monitoring and evaluation of the program.

IRDP is a Centrally Sponsored Scheme which is in operation in all the blocks of the country since 1980. Under this scheme Central funds are allocated to States on the basis of proportion of rural poor in a State to the total rural poor in the country. The IRDP has been successful in providing incremental income to the poor families, but in most cases the incremental income has not been adequate to enable the beneficiaries to cross the poverty line on a sustained basis mainly because of a low per family investment.

- **Development of Women and Children in Rural Areas (DWCRA)**

The special scheme for Development of Women and Children in Rural Areas (DWCRA) aims at strengthening the gender component of IRDP. It was started in the year 1982-83, on a pilot basis, in 50 districts and has now been extended to all the districts of the country. DWCRA is directed at improving the living conditions of women and, thereby, of children through the provision of opportunities for self-employment and access to basic social services. The main strategy adopted under this programme is to facilitate access for poor women to employment, skill upgradation, training, credit and other support services so that the DWCRA women as a group can take up income generating activities for supplementing their incomes. It seeks to encourage collective action in the form of group activities which are known to work better and are more sustainable than the individual effort. It encourages the habit of thrift and credit among poor rural women to make them self-reliant. The programme also envisages that this target group would be the focus for convergence of other services like

family welfare, health care, nutrition, education, child care, safe drinking water, sanitation and shelter to improve the welfare and quality of life of the family and the community.

The Child Care Activities (CCA) component was introduced in the DWCRA programme in 1995-96 with the objective of providing child care services for the children of DWCRA women. Similarly, the Information, Education and Communication (IEC) component was introduced to generate awareness among rural women about the development programmes being implemented for their upliftment and welfare.

In the implementation of DWCRA several shortcomings have also surfaced which has stymied its successful and effective execution in some States. The reasons for these include, among others, (a) improper selection of groups; (b) lack of homogeneity among the group members; (c) selection of non-viable economic activities which are mostly traditional and yield low income; (d) the linkages for supply of raw material and marketing of production are either deficient or not properly planned as a result of which DWCRA groups have become vulnerable to competition; (e) lack of institutional financial support, inadequate training, a non-professional approach and poor access to upgraded technological inputs have deprived DWCRA groups from diversifying into high value addition activities; and (f) inadequacy of staff and their insufficient training and motivation has also affected the overall implementation of the programme. These shortcomings would have to be suitably addressed for the successful implementation of the programme in the Ninth Plan.

- **Rural Landless Employment Guarantee Programme**

Rural Landless Employment Guarantee Programme launched in August 1983 is a supplement to the NREP. Under the programme, the wages to landless labourers are paid partly in money and partly in food grains. The idea behind the programme is that at least one member from each landless family should be provided with 100 days of gainful employment. The projects undertaken under the Programme include improvement of minor irrigation facilities, reclamation of waste land, social forestry and soil conservation. The other projects covered under the Programme include Indira Awas Yojna and the Million Wells Scheme.

- **Pradhan Mantri Gramin Awaas Yojna**

This scheme aimed at creating housing for everyone. It was initiated in 1985. It aimed at creating 20 lakh housing units out of which 13 lakhs were in rural area. This scheme also would give out loans to people at subsidized rates to make houses. It was started in 1999–2000. In 1999–2000, Rs 1438.39 crore was used for this scheme and about 7.98 lakh units were built. In 2000-01 a central outlay of Rs 1710.00 crores was provided for this scheme.

- **Jawahar Rozgar Yojna**

The JRY was launched as a Centrally Sponsored Schemes (CSS) on 1st April, 1989 by merging the National Rural Employment Programme (NREP) and the Rural Landless Employment Guarantee Programme (RLEGP). The main objective of the programme is the generation of additional gainful employment for unemployed and underemployed persons, both men and women, in the rural areas through the creation of rural economic infrastructure, community and social assets with the aim of improving the quality of life of the rural poor. This programme is targeted at people living below the poverty line. However, preference is given to Scheduled Castes/Scheduled Tribes and freed bonded labourers. At least 30 per cent

of the employment is to be provided to women under the Yojana. In practice, however, this programme is self-targeting.

The Evaluation Report also brought into focus certain inadequacies in the programme. It was reported that 57.44 per cent of the elected panchayat heads had not been imparted any training for the implementation of JRY works. The share of women in employment generated under the programme was only 16.59 per cent and 49.47 per cent of the works could not be completed on time on account of shortage of funds. Other shortcomings observed were differentials in the wages paid to male and female workers, non-utilisation of locally available material in a large number of JRY works undertaken by panchayats and lack of discussion of the annual action plans in the Gram Sabha meetings etc.

- **Supply of Improved Toolkits to Rural Artisans (SITRA)**

Launched in July 1992, as a sub-scheme of IRDP in selected districts, this scheme has since been extended to all the districts of the country. Under the scheme, a variety of crafts persons, except weavers, tailors, needle workers and beedi workers, are supplied with a kit of improved hand tools within a financial ceiling of Rs.2000, of which the artisans have to pay 10 per cent and the remaining 90 per cent is a subsidy from the Government of India. The supply of power-driven tools, subject to a ceiling of Rs.4500, is also permitted under this scheme.

Reports from the State Governments indicate that the scheme has been well received by rural artisans. The more popular crafts under this scheme are blacksmith, carpentry, stone craft, leather work, pottery and cane and bamboo work. Prototypes of improved tools in these crafts have been developed by the National Small Industries Corporation (NSIC), Regional Design and Technical Development Centres under the Development Commissioner, Handicrafts and other organisations. The SITRA was evaluated by an independent research organisation, i.e., Development Alternatives, New Delhi, in two Districts of Uttar Pradesh, namely Agra and Aligarh. The findings of this study reaffirm the positive impact of SITRA. It also indicates that the income level of rural artisans has increased substantially with the use of improved tools.

- **Employment Assurance Scheme (EAS)**

The Employment Assurance Scheme (EAS) was launched on 2nd October, 1993 in 1772 identified backward blocks of 257 districts situated in drought prone, desert, tribal and hill areas where the Revamped Public Distribution System (RPDS) was in operation. It is, presently, being implemented in all the 5448 rural blocks of the country. The EAS was restructured w.e.f. 1999-2000 to make it the single wage employment programme. The programme is implemented as a CSS on a cost sharing ratio of 75:25 between the Centre and States. The main objective of the EAS is to provide about 100 days of assured casual manual employment during the lean agricultural season, at statutory minimum wages, to all persons above the age of 18 years and below 60 years who need and seek employment on economically productive and labour intensive social and community works. The primary objective of the EAS is creation of additional wage employment opportunities during the period of acute shortage of wage employment through manual work for the rural poor living below the poverty line. The secondary objective is the creation of durable community, social and economic assets for sustained employment and development. EAS is open to all the needy rural poor living below the poverty line. A maximum of two adults per family are

provided wage employment. While providing employment, preference is given to SCs/STs and parents of child labour withdrawn from hazardous occupations who are below the poverty line. The programme is implemented through the Zilla Parishads (DRDAs in those States where Zilla Parishads do not exist). In areas where Zilla Parishads are not in existence, a committee consisting of MLAs, MPs and other public representatives is constituted for selecting the works. Gram Sabhas is informed about the details of works taken up under the scheme.

- **National Social Assistance Programme (NSAP)**

The NSAP was introduced as a social security programme for the welfare of the poor households. However, it must be recognised that it is not a poverty alleviation scheme but more in the nature of a welfare programme and hence, has a limited role in the overall strategy of poverty alleviation. Moreover, the financial assistance provided to poor households in the case of old age, death of primary bread winner and maternity is in the nature of transfer payments and therefore, it should really form a part of non-plan expenditure.

The NSAP was launched with effect from 15th August, 1995 as a 100 per cent Centrally Sponsored Scheme with the aim to provide social assistance benefit to poor households in the case of old age, death of primary breadwinner and maternity. This represents a significant step towards the fulfilment of the Directive Principles in Articles 41 & 42 of the Constitution. The programme supplements the efforts of the State Governments with the objective of ensuring minimum national levels of well-being and the Central assistance is an addition to the benefit that the States are already providing on Social Protection Schemes or may provide in future. The main features of the three components of the NSAP namely; (i) National Old Age Pension Scheme (NOAPS), (ii) National Family Benefit Scheme (NFBS) and (iii) National Maternity Benefit Scheme (NMBS) are given below:

National Old Age Pension Scheme (NOAPS): This scheme came into effect on 15 August 1995. The scheme provides pension to old people who were above the age of 65 (now 60) who could not find for themselves and did not have any means of subsistence. The pension that was given was Rs 200 a month. This pension is given by the central government. The job of implementation of this scheme in states and union territories is given to panchayats and municipalities. The states contribution may vary depending on the state. The amount of old age pension is Rs. 200 per month for applicants aged 60–79. For applicants aged above 80 years, the amount has been revised in Rs. 500 a month according to the 2011–2012 Budget.

National Family Benefit Scheme (NFBS): This scheme was started in August 1995 by the Government of India. This scheme is sponsored by the state government. It was transferred to the state sector scheme after 2002-03. It is under the community and rural department. This scheme provides a sum of Rs. 20000 to a person of a family who becomes the head of the family after the death of its primary breadwinner. The breadwinner is defined as a person who is above 18 who earns the most for the family and on whose earnings the family survives.

National Maternity Benefit Scheme (NMBS): This scheme provides a sum of 6000 Rs to a pregnant mother in three installments. The women have to be older than 19 years of age. It is

given normally 12–8 weeks before the birth and in case of the death of the child the women can still avail it. The NMBS is implemented by states and union territories with the help of panchayats and municipalities. It is for families below the poverty line. The scheme was updated in 2005-06 into Janani Suraksha Yojana with Rs 1400 for every institutional birth.

- **Area Development Programmes: Drought Prone Area Programme (DPAP), Desert Development Programme (DDP) and Integrated Wastelands Development Programme (IWDP)**

The Drought Prone Area Programme (DPAP), Desert Development Programme (DDP) and Integrated Wastelands Development Programme (IWDP) are being implemented with effect from 1.4.1995 on a watershed basis, as per the recommendations of the Technical Committee on DPAP and DDP headed by Dr. C.H. Hanumantha Rao.

Drought Prone Area Programme (DPAP)

DPAP aims at to minimise the adverse effects of drought on production of crops and livestock and productivity of land, water and human resources ultimately leading to the drought proofing of the affected areas. It also aims at promoting overall economic development and improving the socio-economic conditions of the resource poor and disadvantaged sections inhabiting the programme areas. The DPAP is in operation in 947 blocks of 161 districts in 13 States.

Desert Development Programme (DDP)

DDP has been envisaged as an essentially land based activity and conceived as a long-term measure for restoration of ecological balance by conserving, developing and harnessing land, water, livestock and human resources. The main objectives of this programme are: (i) combating drought and desertification; (ii) encouraging restoration of ecological balance; (iii) mitigating the adverse effects of drought and adverse edaphoclimatic conditions on crops and livestock and productivity of land, water and human resources; (iv) promoting economic development of village community; and (v) improving socio economic conditions of the resource poor and disadvantaged sections of village community viz; assetless and women.

Integrated Wastelands Development Programme (IWDP)

IWDP is a 100 per cent Central Sector scheme. The basic objective of this scheme is to take up integrated wastelands development based on village/micro watershed plans. The stakeholders prepare these plans after taking into consideration land capability, site conditions and local needs. The scheme also helps in generation of employment in rural areas besides enhancing people's participation in the wasteland's development programmes at all stages. This leads to equitable sharing of benefits and sustainable development. The major activities taken up under the scheme are: (i) soil and moisture conservation measures like terracing, bunding, trenching, vegetative barriers etc.; (ii) planting and sowing of multi-purpose trees, shrubs, grasses, legumes and pasture land development; (iii) encouraging natural regeneration; (iv) promotion of agro-forestry and horticulture; (v) wood substitution and fuel wood conservation measures; (vi) measures needed to disseminate technology; training, extension and creation of greater degree of awareness among the participants; and (vii) encouraging people's participation.

- **Panchayati Raj Institutions**

The Seventy Third Constitutional Amendment Act, 1992 has given impetus to democratic decentralisation in the country by conferring Constitutional status on the Panchayati Raj Institutions (PRIs). The Provisions of the Panchayats (Extension to the Scheduled Areas) Act 1996 has come into force with effect from 24th December, 1996 and extend Panchayats to the tribal areas of eight States, viz; Andhra Pradesh, Bihar, Gujarat, Himachal Pradesh, Maharashtra, Madhya Pradesh, Orissa and Rajasthan. It intends to enable tribal society to assume control over its own destiny, preserve its cultural ethos and conserve its traditional rights over natural resources. Article 243 (I) of the Constitution provides for the constitution of State Finance Commission (SFC) to review the financial position of Panchayats and to make recommendations regarding principles governing distribution of net taxes between State Governments and the Panchayats, assignment of taxes and grant-in-aid to Panchayats. Article 243 (G) of the 73rd Constitutional Amendment Act endows the PRIs with the requisite financial and administrative powers to enable them to function as effective institutions of local self-government. It envisages the establishment of a democratic decentralised development process through people's participation in decision-making, in implementation and in the delivery process. In order to achieve this objective, the Constitution provides for devolution of powers and responsibilities upon Panchayats at appropriate levels for economic development and social justice in respect of 29 Subjects as listed in the Eleventh Schedule of the Constitution. The State Governments are required to constitute District Planning Committees (DPCs) as envisaged under Article 243 (Z) and (D) of the 74th Constitutional amendment Act to facilitate the process of decentralised planning. DPCs are to be set up in each district to prepare composite plans covering both urban and rural areas. The Year of 1999-2000 was declared as 'Year of the Gram Sabha' by the Government of India in recognition that the Gram Sabha is potentially the most significant institution for participatory democracy and decentralisation. The State Governments have been requested to initiate measures to energise Gram Sabhas. To ensure greater transparency and accountability, attention of State Governments have also been drawn to the importance of social audit in implementation of development programmes especially rural development programmes through Gram Sabha. In the light of 73rd Constitutional Amendment Act, the District Rural Development Agencies (DRDAs) are also being restructured to suit the changed scenario. DRDAs would have to work under the overall control and supervision of the Zilla Parishads. In order to make decentralised development a success, a time bound training programme, in phases, has been initiated for the new entrants into the PRIs so as to make them familiar with the implementation of various programmes, technologies and other requisite information.

- **Land Reforms**

Land reforms have been viewed both as a means for achieving redistributive justice and as means for attaining higher levels of agricultural production and income in the rural areas. Access to land is still a major source of employment and income in rural areas. Therefore, the issue of agrarian restructuring continues to receive the priority. The major components of the Land Reforms Policy include among others, detection and distribution of ceiling surplus lands, tenancy reforms, consolidation of land holdings, providing access to poor on common lands and wastelands, preventing the alienation of tribal lands and providing land rights to

women. Further, for the successful implementation of land reforms, updating of land records by traditional methods as well as through computerisation is an essential prerequisite. Since land is a state subject, the responsibility of implementing land reforms rests with the State Governments. However, two Centrally Sponsored Schemes (CSS) viz; 'Strengthening of Revenue Administration and Updating of Land Records' (SRA & ULR) and 'Computerization of Land Records' (CLR) are being implemented by the Ministry of Rural Development. The CSS of 'Strengthening of Revenue Administration and Updating of Land Records' is designed to provide support to the ongoing programmes of tenancy reforms.

- **Million Wells Scheme (MWS)**

The Million Wells Scheme (MWS) was launched as a sub-scheme of the National Rural Employment Programme (NREP) and the Rural Landless Employment Guarantee Programme (RLEGP) during the year 1988-89. After the merger of the two programmes in April 1989 into the Jawahar Rozgar Yojana (JRY), the MWS continued as a sub-scheme of JRY till December 1995. The MWS was delinked from JRY and made into an independent scheme with effect from 1.1.1996. The MWS is a Centrally Sponsored Scheme. The scheme was primarily intended to provide open irrigation wells, free of cost, to individual, poor, small and marginal farmers belonging to Scheduled Castes/Scheduled Tribes and freed bonded labourers with a 20 per cent earmarking of JRY funds. Tubewells and borewells are not permitted under the Scheme. Where wells are not feasible due to geological factors, other minor irrigation works can be undertaken such as irrigation tanks, water harvesting structures as also development of land belonging to small and marginal farmers.

- **Swaranjayanti Gram Swarozgar Yojna**

The single self-employment programme of Swaranjayanti Gram Swarozgar Yojna was launched in April 1999. Million Wells Scheme, and Development of Women and Children in Rural Areas have been merged in the Scheme. The objective of restructuring was to make the programme more effective in providing sustainable incomes through micro enterprises.

The SGSY lays emphasis on the following:

- focused approach to poverty alleviation
- capitalizing advantages of group lending
- overcoming the problems associated with multiplicity of programmes

SGSY is conceived as a holistic programme of micro enterprises covering all aspects of self-employment viz. organisation of the rural poor into self-help groups (SHGs) and their capacity building, planning of activity clusters, infrastructure build up, technology, credit and marketing. Micro enterprises in the rural areas are sought to be established by building on the potential of the rural poor. The objective of the programme is to bring the existing poor families above the poverty line.

Under the SGSY, the focus is on vulnerable sections among the rural poor with SCs/STs accounting for 50 per cent, women 40 per cent and the disabled 3 per cent of the beneficiaries. The list of BPL households, identified through BPL census, duly approved by the Gram Sabha forms the basis for assistance to families under SGSY. The beneficiaries (also called Swarozgaris) could be individuals or groups. While the identification of individual beneficiaries is made through a participatory approach, the programme lays emphasis on organisation of poor into SHGs and their capacity building. The SHG may consist of 10 to 20 persons. In case of minor irrigation, and in case of the disabled, the

minimum is 5 persons. The SGSY is a credit-cum-subsidy programme, with credit as the critical component and subsidy as a minor and enabling element. Accordingly, the SGSY envisages greater involvement of banks and promotion of multiple credit rather than a one-time credit injection.

Funds under the SGSY are shared by the Centre and the States in the ratio of 75:25. The Central allocation is distributed in relation to the incidence of poverty in the States. However, additional parameters like absorption capacity and special requirements can also be considered.

- **Jawahar Gram Samridhi Yojna (JGSY)**

Jawahar Gram Samridhi Yojana (JGSY) is the restructured, streamlined and comprehensive version of the erstwhile Jawahar Rozgar Yojana (JRY). It was started on 1 April 1999. The main aim of this programme was development of rural areas. The JGSY is implemented as a CSS with funding in the ratio of 75:25 between the Centre and the States. The primary objective of JGSY is creation of demand driven community village infrastructure including durable assets at the village level and assets to enable the rural poor to increase the opportunities for sustained employment. The secondary objective is generation of supplementary employment for the unemployed poor in the rural areas. The wage employment under the programme is given to Below Poverty Lines (BPL) families. The wages under the programme are either the minimum wages notified by the States or higher wages as fixed by the States through the prescribed procedure. The wage material ratio of 60:40 can be suitably relaxed so as to enable the building up of demand driven rural infrastructure. However, efforts may be made to ensure that labour intensive works are taken up with sustainable low-cost technology. Under the programme, village panchayats have the sole authority for the preparation of the Annual Action Plan and its implementation, which needs to be accepted by the Gram Sabha. Thus, the Gram Sabha is empowered to approve schemes. The completion of the incomplete works is to be given priority over new works and works which cannot be completed within two financial years are not to be included. At the village level, the entire work relating to coordination, review, supervision and monitoring of the programme is the responsibility of the village panchayat.

- **Annapurna**

This scheme was started by the government in 1999–2000 to provide food to senior citizens who cannot take care of themselves and are not under the National Old Age Pension Scheme (NOAPS), and who have no one to take care of them in their village. This scheme would provide 10 kg of free food grains a month for the eligible senior citizens. They mostly target groups of 'poorest of the poor' and 'indigent senior citizens'. The Gram Panchayats would be required to identify, prepare and display a list of such persons after giving wide publicity.

- **Rural Housing – Indira Awaas Yojna (IAY)**

In the Ninth Plan, the Special Action Plan for Social Infrastructure has identified 'Housing' as one of the priority areas. It aims at providing 'Housing for All' and facilitates construction of 20 lakh additional dwelling units, of which 13 lakh dwelling units are to be constructed in rural areas. The composite housing strategy for the Ninth Plan is a multipronged strategy which has been operationalised w.e.f. 1999-2000. However, an additional component has been added, namely, conversion of unserviceable kutcha houses to semi pucca houses.

Samagra Awaas Yojana, a comprehensive housing scheme, was launched in 1999- 2000 on pilot project basis in one block in each of 25 districts of 24 States and in one Union Territory with a view to ensuring integrated provision of shelter, sanitation and drinking water.

- **National Rural Employment Guarantee Act (NREGA)**

The NREGA bill notified in 2005 and came into force in 2006 and further modified it as the Mahatma Gandhi National Rural Employment Guarantee Act (MGNREGA) in Oct 2, 2009. This scheme guarantees 100 days now 150 days of paid work to people in the rural areas. The scheme has proved to be a major boost in Indian rural population's income. The Ministry of Rural Development (MRD) is the nodal Ministry for the implementation of NREGA. It is responsible for ensuring timely and adequate resource support to the States and to the Central Council.

National Rural Employment Programme is the new name for the Original Food for Work Programme. It is centrally sponsored with the Central government providing 50% assistance. Under the Programme the target is to create additional employment of the order 300-400 million men days annually. The beneficiaries are to be the unemployed and the under-employed persons. A critical assessment of the performance under the Plan shows that while funds are put in the programme liberally the output in terms of employment generation remains well below the target. The employment provided is of short duration and the wages paid are less than the prevailing market rates. Even the selection of beneficiaries is not always above board.

- **Training of Rural Youth for Self-Employment (TRYSEM)**

The Scheme of TRYSEM, a facilitating component of IRDP, aims at providing basic technical and entrepreneurial skills to the rural poor in the age group of 18 to 35 years to enable them to take up income generating activities. With a view to strengthening this programme, several initiatives were taken in the Eighth Plan which include, among others, an increase in the stipend and honorarium rates; emphasis on professionalised training through the established and recognized institutes like ITIs, Community Polytechnics, Krishi Vigyan Kendras etc., exploring the possibilities of setting up production groups from amongst TRYSEM trainees for undertaking ancillary activities like manufacture and assembly of modern items of production; utilization of TRYSEM infrastructure funds for the strengthening of Nirmithi Kendras (Rural Building Centres) sponsored by HUDCO for training of youth under TRYSEM in the trades of low cost housing and the setting up of mini-ITIs at the block level to strengthen the training infrastructure for the rural youth.

Conclusions

Poverty and unemployment have been the bane of India since long. Their reduction has been one of the major goals of India's development planning since the beginning of the planning era in 1951-52 and the planning process has been sensitive to the needs of the poor. Poverty alleviation schemes and programmes have been in pace for a long time now. The programmes and schemes have been modified, consolidated, expanded and improved over time. In addition, initial endowments of physical infrastructure and human resources did contribute to the inter-state variations in the performance. A careful examination of the poverty alleviation programmes reveals that the planners have made the assumption that the poor constitute a homogeneous category. The planners made no attempt to segment the group in terms of common characteristics and their requirements. A distinction has to be made

between two categories of poor, namely, those who have some skills and thus can take up self-employment and others who are to be provided with wage-employment. Each category should be treated separately by appropriate policy measures. Self-employment is a major form of employment in the rural areas and this fact must not be ignored in the strategy of poverty alleviation. Further, dependence on wage employment alone to tackle the problem of poverty will lead to total dependence of the poor on employers. A major limitation of the existing poverty alleviation strategy is that it has no programmes for these households who neither have assets nor skills, and in addition, do not have any able-bodied adult member and thus cannot benefit from wage employment programmes. For such a category separate policy measure would be required. Moreover, poor targeting is reflected in the high proportion of non-poor and other non-eligible persons among the beneficiaries under these programmes. It is also true that outlays on targeted poverty alleviation programmes have increased rapidly both in absolute terms and relative to total public sector plan outlays. The poverty alleviation programmes were revamped and refocused during the Ninth Plan to increase their effectiveness. During the Tenth Plan, those programmes that provide self-employment and wage employment to the poor would be implemented with greater vigour. The growth-oriented approach for poverty alleviation has been reinforced in the Tenth Plan by focusing on specific sectors, which provide greater opportunities for the poor to participate in the growth process. Anti-poverty programmes have been strengthened and restructured through special programmes for the weaker sections of the society. In spite of various strategies adopted by center and state governments, a large chunk of population in rural areas is living below the poverty line and can hardly meet their basic necessities of life. Out of the total population in the rural parts of India, 25.7% is living below the poverty line. Many of the programmes are not efficiently working in rural sector. There is a dire need to implement and execute the programmes at the grass root level.

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